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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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MOTIVATIONS FOR STUDENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN SPORTING ACTIVITIES IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IMENTI NORTH SUB-COUNTY, MERU COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract

This study sought to establish the motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in Public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. Sports as co-curriculum activity in schools have had a significant value on the holistic development of students. This study employed a descriptive research design. 15 schools were identified in the study using stratified sampling based on the zones. The sample size comprised of 15 principals, 15 games masters, 15 class teachers, and 225 form three students. Data was obtained through structured questionnaires, oral interviews, primary and secondary sources to ensure the reliability and validity of the study. After the data was collected, it was sorted, cleaned and coded. Subsequently, the data was keyed into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 27) for processing. Descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized for data analysis. This study established the motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in Public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. The study concluded that the students are engaged in sporting activities to achieve physical fitness, for socialization, to refresh their minds, to enhance their health and to manage their stress and anxiety, and also to enhance their academic performance among public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. The study recommends that School administrators should enlighten students on the benefits of engaging in sports and spend funds meant for sports to improve sports facilities.

Keywords: Motivation, Sporting Activities, Students

Introduction

Many schools pay more importance to academic activities to the detriment of other activities such as sports and physical education. According to Weeldenburg et al. (2020), physical education may be defined as the programs created to cater to the physical skills of the learners based on their age, skill level, and unique needs. In most cases, physical education involves at least 90 minutes of physical activity per week (Weeldenburg et al., 2020). Sing et al. (2019) observe that many children are affected by obesity and diseases such as diabetes due to the lack of physical activity. Many schools are reducing time for physical education in favour of academic activities such as teaching math and sciences. In Kenya, some teachers use the time allocated for physical activities to advance the syllabus (Onyancha, 2018). Arguments by Sing et al. (2019) prove that these institutions are mistaken to reduce the instructional time for physical education since there is adequate evidence to suggest that it contributes to academic excellence. Physical education improves the physical, social, emotional, and cognitive areas of learning thus, it improves academic performance. Therefore, it made it necessary for this study to establish the motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya.

Research Questions

- i. What are the key motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?

- ii. How do class teachers perceive students' participation in sports in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?
- iii. How do games teachers perceive students' participation in sports in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?

Hypotheses

- H₀₁ There are no significant differences in motivation for engaging in sports between male and female students in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya.
- H₀₂ There are no significant variations in students' motivation for engaging in sports based on school type in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Physical Activities and Students' Well-being

During the physical education sessions, instructors explain the benefits of physical activities to the physical health of students. As explained by Weeldenburg et al. (2020) many youths and children in the world are obese. Being overweight contributes to other issues such as diabetes and cardiovascular issues that affect the quality of life of the students. Lifestyle diseases such as diabetes affect the ability of the student to concentrate on academic performance and in some instances, the student may be absent from school for a long time. These outcomes contribute to poor academic performance by the students, proving that physical activities are necessary to improve performance. O'Neill et al., (2017) posited that when students understand the implications of physical activities on their physical well-being and academic attainments, they are more likely to undertake healthy measures such as indulging in sports. Moreover, indulging in physical activities reduces obesity which is associated with low self-esteem and stress (O'Neill et al., 2015; Hacifazlıoğlu, 2021). Therefore, physical education can improve the academic performance of students by preventing some diseases such as diabetes and self-esteem issues associated with obesity.

Social Activities and Students Well-being

Students interact with one another during physical education. Some scholars assert that people interact and communicate during physical activities (Brailovskaia, et al., 2018). As observed earlier these interactions help individuals to build a sense of togetherness and belonging (De PradaCreo, et al., 2020). When students have good communication skills, they can interact with each other and collaborate effectively in academic projects. Moreover, Brailovskaia et al., (2018) argue that students also learn other social skills such as tolerance and respect towards others. These skills are useful in attaining better educational outcomes since they are not only determined through test grades but through development in all areas that will allow the student to become successful in their professional and personal life (O'Neill et al., 2017).

Emotional Activities and Students Well-being

Physical education helps to relieve stress and anxiety. During physical education, the instructor may guide the students to perform a variety of physical activities such as jogging, yoga, aerobics, and jump rope. During physical activity, the brain secretes more endorphins (Meenapriya, et al., 2018). These peptides work on the opiate receptors in the brain and they increase the feeling of pleasure and well-being for the individual. This means that increased endorphin secretion in the brain as a result of physical activity may relieve stress. When

students are less stressed and happy, they are more likely to concentrate on their academics and as a result, they would perform better than stressed ones (Kuan et al., 2019). Therefore, physical education improves academic performance by relieving bad emotions such as stress and sadness.

Cognitive Activities and Students Well-being

Limiting the time for physical education also limits the cognitive development of learners. Munyua (2019), averred that physical activities contribute immensely to brain functioning and development. During physical education exercises, the heart pumps more blood to the brain. Additionally, physical activity increases the release of growth factors that stimulate the development of new brain cells (Brenner et al., 2019; Hacifazlıoğlu, 2021). Additional brain cells increase cognitive functions such as short-term and long-term memories which are important in academic development. Hence, physical education is expected to improve academic performance in students by improving their physical, social, emotional, and cognitive aspects.

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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design. The purpose of descriptive research design is to determine and report the way things are (Mugenda & Mugenda 2013). According to Kothari (2015), the main purpose of descriptive research is to describe the state of affairs as it exists at present. This is supported by Orodho (2009) who argues that a descriptive survey can be used when collecting information about people's attitudes, opinions, habits or any of a variety of education or social issues. According to Ngechu (2004), a research design is a detailed outline of procedures and approaches on how data is gathered for exhaustive evaluation, which consists of data identification, data collection tools and techniques, how the tools are administered and how the collected data is organized and analysed. Hence, descriptive research design was appropriate in establishing the motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. A descriptive research design was appropriate because of its suitability

in gathering data on the perception of the population in addressing research questions (Ponto, 2015).

FINDINGS

Answers to Research Questions

The study sought to establish the motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. In this section, answers will be providing to the stated research questions and hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question One

What are the key motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?

Table 1: Motivations for students' involvement in sporting activities

Motivation Item	SA		A	
	F	%	F	%
I engage in sporting activities to be physically fit	32	15.8	171	84.2
Sporting activities gives me an avenue for socialization	95	46.8	108	53.2
Sporting activities refreshes my mind	151	74.4	52	25.6
Sporting activities enhances my health	34	16.7	169	83.3
Sporting activities help reduce stress and anxiety	107	52.7	96	47.3

Item five of the principals' questionnaire sought to establish the motivations behind students' involvement in sporting activities. The majority of the participants indicated that students engage in sports as a way of breaking the monotony of reading. Some participants pointed out that students engage in sports as an avenue of socialization. They noted that students value so much the time they are outside the school for co-curriculum activities and would do anything within their means not to miss such an opportunity. A few participants indicated that students engage in sports for physical fitness.

Research Question Two

How do class teachers perceive students' participation in sports in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?

Table 2: Motivation for students' participation in sports: Class teachers' perspective

Motivation Item	A		D	
	F	%	F	%
The school avails sufficient resources for sporting activities	11	73.3	4	26.7
The school has adequate playground for sports	9	60.0	6	40.0
The school effectively motivates teachers who supervise students in sports	6	40.0	9	60.0
The school has allocated adequate time for sports in the school routine program	9	60.0	6	40.0
Students are motivated to participate in sports	9	60.0	6	40.0
The school participates in interschool tournament other than the scheduled sports calendar activities	6	40.0	9	60.0

The school organizes for interschool tournaments	2	13.3	13	86.7
The school organizes for inter-class/inter-dormitory sports	11	73.3	4	26.7
The schools avail sufficient budgetary allocation for sports	6	40.0	9	60.0
The schools budget for sports has been on the rise	5	33.3	10	66.7

The class teachers' perception of motivation for students' involvement in sporting activities was examined using ten parameters captured in items of the class teachers' questionnaire. Item 1 of the class teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school availed sufficient resources for sporting activities. As shown in Table 2, nearly three-quarters of the participants (73.3%) agreed while 26.7% disagreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the class teachers included in the study, the schools provided adequate resources for sporting activities. Hence, the students participated in sporting activities as a result of sufficient resources availed by the school. Item 2 of the class teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school had an adequate playground for sports. The majority of the participants (60.0%) agreed while 40.0% disagreed. These results signify that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, the schools had adequate playgrounds for sports. Nearly two-thirds of the participants upheld this opinion. Hence, students were motivated to participate in sporting activities due to adequate playgrounds.

Item 3 of the class teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school effectively motivated teachers who supervised students in sports. The majority of the participants (60.0%) disagreed while 40.0% agreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, teachers who supervised students in sports were not adequately motivated. Nearly two-thirds of the participants supported this opinion. Hence, the motivation of teachers who supervised students during games was not a motivation for students' participation in sporting activities. Item 4 of the class teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school had allocated adequate time for sports in the school routine program. Most of the participants (60.0%) agreed while 40.0% disagreed. These results signify that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, the time allocated for sports in the school routine program was adequate. Only less than half of the participants held a divergent opinion.

Regarding Item 5 of the class teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether students were motivated to participate in sports. Many of the participants (60.0%) agreed while 40.0% disagreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, the students were well motivated to participate in sports. Only less than half of the participants opined that the students were not well motivated. Regarding Item 6 of the class teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school participated in interschool tournaments other than the scheduled sports calendar activities. Most of the participants (60.0%) disagreed while 40.0% agreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, most schools did not participate in interschool tournaments other than the scheduled sports calendar activities. Only less than half of the participants pointed out that they did participate.

Regarding Item 7 of the class teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school organized interschool tournaments. Many of the participants (86.7%) disagreed while 13.3% agreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, most schools in Imenti North Sub County did not organize interschool tournaments. Nearly nine-tenths of the participants upheld this opinion. Regarding Item 8 of the class teachers'

questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school organizes inter-class/inter-dormitory sports. Most of the participants (73.3%) agreed while 26.7% disagreed. These results imply that in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, most schools organized inter-class/inter-dormitory sports. Nearly three-quarters of the participants supported this opinion.

Regarding Item 9 of the class teachers’ questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school availed sufficient budgetary allocation for sports. Many of the participants (60.0%) disagreed while 40.0% agreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, the school’s budgetary allocation for sports was not sufficient. Only less than half of the participants opined that it was adequate. Regarding Item 10 of the class teachers’ questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school budget for sports has been on the rise. Two-thirds of the participants (66.7%) disagreed while 33.3% agreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the class teachers interviewed, the school budget for sports had a downward trajectory. Only a third of the participants pointed out an upward trajectory.

Research Question Three

How do games teachers perceive students’ participation in sports in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya?

Table 3: Motivation for students’ participation in sports: Games teachers’ perspective

Motivation Item	A		D	
	F	%	F	%
The school avails sufficient resources for sporting activities	9	60.0	6	40.0
The school has adequate playground for sports	8	53.3	7	46.7
The school effectively motivates teachers who supervise students in sports	10	66.7	5	33.3
The school has allocated adequate time for sports in the school routine program	10	66.7	5	33.3
Students are motivated to participate in sports	10	66.7	5	33.3
The school participates in interschool tournament other than the scheduled sports calendar activities	8	53.3	7	46.7
The school organizes for interschool tournaments	2	13.3	13	86.7
The school organizes for inter-class/inter-dormitory sports	15	100.0	0	0.0
The schools avails sufficient budgetary allocation for sports	8	53.3	7	46.7
The schools budget for sports has been on the rise	9	60.0	6	40.0

The games teachers’ perception of motivation for students’ involvement in sporting activities was examined using ten parameters captured in item four of the games teachers’ questionnaire. Item 1 of the games teachers’ questionnaire sought to establish whether the school availed sufficient resources for sporting activities. As shown in Table 3, nearly two-thirds of the participants (60.0%) agreed while 40.0% disagreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the games teachers included in the study, the schools provided adequate resources for sporting activities. Hence, the students participated in sporting activities as a result of adequate resources availed by the school. Item 2 of the games teachers’ questionnaire sought to establish whether the school had an adequate playground for sports. The majority

of the participants (53.3%) agreed while 46.7% disagreed. These results signify that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, the schools had adequate playgrounds for sports. More than half of the participants upheld this opinion. Hence, students were motivated to participate in sporting activities due to adequate playgrounds.

Item 3 of the games teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school effectively motivated teachers who supervised students in sports. The majority of the participants (66.7%) agreed while 33.3% disagreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, teachers who supervised students in sports were adequately motivated. Two-thirds of the participants upheld this opinion. Hence, the motivation of teachers who supervised students during games was a motivation for students' participation in sporting activities. Item 4 of the games teachers' questionnaire sought to establish whether the school had allocated adequate time for sports in the school routine program. The majority of the participants (66.7%) agreed while 33.3% disagreed. These results signify that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, the time allocated for sports in the school routine program was adequate. Only a third of the participants held a divergent opinion.

Regarding Item 5 of the games teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether students were motivated to participate in sports. The majority of the participants (66.7%) agreed while 33.3% disagreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, the students were well motivated to participate in sports. Only a third of the participants opined that the students were not well motivated. Regarding Item 6 of the games teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school participated in interschool tournaments other than the scheduled sports calendar activities. The majority of the participants (53.3%) agreed while 46.7% disagreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, most schools participated in interschool tournaments other than the scheduled sports calendar activities. Only less than half of the participants pointed out that they did not participate.

Regarding Item 7 of the games teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school organized interschool tournaments. The majority of the participants (86.7%) disagreed while 13.3% agreed. These results imply that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, most schools in Imenti North Sub County did not organize interschool tournaments. Nearly nine-tenths of the participants upheld this opinion. Regarding Item 8 of the games teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school organizes inter-class/inter-dormitory sports. All the participants (100.0%) pointed out that the school organizes inter-class/inter-dormitory sports. Hence, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, all schools organized for inter-class/inter-dormitory sports. None of the participants held a divergent opinion.

Regarding Item 9 of the class teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school availed sufficient budgetary allocation for sports. The majority of the participants (53.3%) agreed while 46.7% disagreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed, the school budgetary allocation for sports was sufficient. Only less than half of the participants opined that it was not adequate. Regarding Item 10 of the games teachers' questionnaire, the participants were asked whether the school budget for sports has been on the rise. The majority of the participants (60.0%) agreed while 40.0% disagreed. These results suggest that, in the opinion of the games teachers interviewed the school budget for

sports had an upward trajectory. Only less than half of the participants pointed out a downward trajectory.

Test of Hypothesis One

H01 There are no significant differences in motivation for engaging in sports between male and female students in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya.

Table 4a: Motivation for Engaging in Sports Based on Gender

Test Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Motivation for engaging in sports	Male	100	21.8	1.70	0.170
	Female	99	22.2	1.69	0.170

To effectively evaluate students’ motivation for engaging in sports, the study compared the students’ motivation between gender and school type. This necessitated the formation of students’ motivation to engage in sports scale. The correlation among responses from the five items on students’ motivation for engaging in sports was high. The answers to the five questions were summed up to create a student’s motivation for engaging in sports scale. Cronbach’s coefficient alpha obtained was .821; hence, the internal consistency of the items related to students' motivation for engaging in sports was good. A T-test was performed to examine the difference in students’ motivation for engaging in sports between males and females. Results displayed in Table 4 showed that the mean students’ motivation for engaging in sports score of females was 22.2 (SD = 1.69) while that of their counterparts was 21.8 (SD = 1.70). This means that students’ motivation for engaging in sports scores for females was higher than that of males. An independent-sample t-test indicated that the difference in students’ motivation for engaging in sports scores for males and females was not statistically significant. The P-value was greater than .05 as shown in Table 4. Hence, the study did not establish a significant relationship between students’ motivation for engaging in sports and gender.

Table 4b: Motivation for engaging in sports based on gender: Independent samples test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
	F	Sig.	T	Df	P - Value	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	.206	.651	-1.378	197	.170	-0.332	0.241
Equal variances not assumed			-1.379	197.0	.170	-0.332	0.241

One-way ANOVA was done to examine the relationship between students' motivation for engaging in sports and school type. As shown in Table 4.42, the mean of students' motivation

for engaging in sports score for participants in sub-county schools was 24.0 (SD = .99), followed by participants in county schools who posted a mean of 22.1 (SD = .90). Further, the mean for participants in extra county school was 20.4 (SD = .48), while the mean for participants in national schools was 20.0 (SD = .23).

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂ There are no significant variations in students' motivation for engaging in sports based on school type in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya.

Table 5a: Motivation for sports based on school type: Homogeneity of variances

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	P - Value
93.886	3	195	.000

One-way ANOVA assumes that the variances are homogenous. To test this assumption, a homogeneity test of variance was performed. The p-value of the Levene statistic is less than .05 indicating that the variances are statistically different as shown in Table 5a. Though the Bonferroni procedure assumes equal variances, the sample size for this study was large. This reduced the problem, hence the ANOVA was interpreted.

Table 5b: Motivation for engaging in sports based on school type: ANOVA statistics

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-Value
Between Groups	448.5	3	149.5	234.2	.000
Within Groups	124.5	195	0.6		
Total	573.0	198			

The ANOVA table provides information on whether the means for the different groups are statistically different or not. When the p-value is less than .05 then the means for the different groups are not all equal. There is much difference between the two Mean Squares (149.5 and 0.6), resulting in a significant difference $F(3, 195) = 234.2, p < .001$ as shown in Table 5b. It was found that the means of the four school categories were not all equal. This necessitated a multiple comparison table to be able to point out which groups had significantly different means.

DISCUSSION

To answer the research questions and to carry out hypotheses testing, the student's class teachers', games teachers' and principals' opinions on motivation for students' involvement in sporting activities were sought. The results are discussed below.

The learners' perception of motivation for students' involvement in sporting activities was examined using five parameters captured in the items of the students' questionnaire. Item 1 of the students' questionnaire sought to establish whether the participants engaged in sporting activities to be physically fit. As shown in Table 1, all the participants pointed out that they participated in sporting activities to be physically fit, where 84.2% agreed and 15.8% strongly agreed. These results signify that the students engaged in sporting activities to achieve physical fitness. None of the participants held a divergent opinion. These results are in line with the findings of Sing et al. (2019) who observed that many children are affected by obesity and diseases such as diabetes due to the lack of physical activity. Item 2 of the students' questionnaire sought to establish whether the participants engaged in sporting activities as an

avenue for socialization. All the participants specified that sporting activities gave them an avenue for socialization, where 53.2% agreed and 46.38% strongly agreed. These results imply that the students perceived sporting activities as an avenue for socialization. None of the participants held a divergent opinion. These results support the findings of De PradaCreo et al. (2020) who posited that students interact and communicate during physical activities. These interactions help individuals to build a sense of togetherness and belonging. In addition, Brailovskaia et al. (2018) asserted that students learn social skills such as tolerance towards others and respect during sports. These skills are useful in attaining better educational outcomes since they are not only determined through test grades but through development in all areas that will allow the student to become successful in their professional and personal life.

Item 3 of the students' questionnaire sought to establish whether sporting activities refreshed the participant's mind. All the participants indicated that sporting activities refreshed their minds, where 47.4% strongly agreed and 25.6% agreed. These results suggest that the students participated in sporting activities to refresh their minds. None of the participants held a differing opinion. These results are in line with the findings of Meenapriya et al. (2018) who observed that during physical activity, the brain secretes more endorphins. These secretions work on the opiate receptors in the brain, and they increase the feeling of pleasure and well-being for the individual. This means that increased endorphin secretion in the brain as a result of physical activity may relieve stress. When students are less stressed and happy, they are more likely to concentrate on their academics and as a result, they would perform better than stressed ones. Therefore, physical education improves academic performance by relieving bad emotions such as stress and sadness.

Item 4 of the students' questionnaire sought to establish whether sporting activities enhanced the participants' health. All the participants believed that sporting activities enhanced their health, where 83.3% agreed and 16.7% strongly agreed. These results infer that the students participated in sporting activities to enhance their health. None of the participants held a different opinion. These results are in line with the findings of Sing et al. (2019) who posited that engagement in sporting activities greatly improves the health of the participant by stabilizing the range of key vitals like blood pressure, sugar levels and heartbeats. Item 20(v) of the students' questionnaire sought to establish whether sporting activities helped reduce stress and anxiety for the participants. All the participants pointed out that sports activities helped reduce their stress and anxiety, where 52.7% strongly agreed and 47.3% agreed. These results suggest that the students engaged in sports activities to manage their stress and anxiety. All the participants supported this opinion. These findings agree with those of Munyua (2019) who established that sporting activities improve academic performance by relieving bad emotions such as stress and sadness.

CONCLUSION

The study established the motivation for student involvement in sporting activities in public secondary schools in Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. Some of the major drives identified for participation in sports were physical fitness, socialization, mental refreshment, health improvement, and stress relief. Both class teachers and games teachers recognized the role of sports in promoting students' wellbeing; however, they noted challenges such as inadequate resources and few interschool tournaments. Based on gender, the study found no significant difference between male and female students in motivation to participate in sports. There was significant variation, however in the motivational level of students based on school type, because it tended to be higher in sub-county schools compared

to national and extra-county schools. This signifies that resources, type of school, and infrastructure used for sporting are very relevant and influential in determining the participation of students in sporting activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is therefore imperative that the following recommendations be adopted and implemented in school:

- Policymakers should find measures to enlighten students on the benefit of engaging in sports as well as encourage them to engage in sports to better attendance rates, lower dropout rates and improve academic performance.
- Administrative heads of schools should spend funds meant for sports to improve sports facilities.
- Policymakers should adjust academic schedules to provide adequate time for physical activities, ensuring that students can engage in sports without compromising their academic performance.
- Even though no significant differences were found in motivation between male and female students, schools should still consider offering a diverse range of sports that cater to the interests of both genders, ensuring inclusivity and broad participation across the student body.
- Efforts should be made to ensure that all school types - whether national, extra-county, county, or sub-county – have equal access to sports facilities, equipment, and qualified staff, to bridge the gap in motivation levels observed between different school categories.

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